

Optimum utilization of COVID-19 Testing Kits using the Principles of Computer Science Binary Search Algorithm in Pooled Sample Testing

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Abstract: Amid of the ongoing global outbreak of Novel Corona Virus (COVID-19) pandemic, most countries of the world are working to maximize their testing capacity to fight against COVID-19. For developing countries like India, this COVID-19 testing capacity building activity seems a monstrous task, specifically due to a global shortage of testing kits and naive phase of domestic productions of testing kits. The research communities and government organizations across the world are trying to devise a methodology to grapple with this global shortage of testing kits. Pooled Sample Testing is one such methodology that has emerged recently which utilizes the testing kits optimally, where the positivity rate is low. For optimal utilization of testing kits, this article provides the theoretical study of Pooled Sample testing methodology of COVID-19 using the principles of Computer Science, Data Structure Binary Search Algorithm. This study will explain how using new methodology using the principles of Binary Search Algorithm, there can be a further reduction in the number of testing kits required for identifying individual positive specimens.

Keywords: COVID-19, Pooled Sample Testing, Computer Science, Data Structure and Binary Search Algorithm.

I. INTRODUCTION

To withstand in this ongoing fight against COVID-19 global crisis, testing is emerged out a key weapon and various types of testing methodology are adopted to cure and trace out the spread of infections. Pooled Sample Testing [1] is one such methodology that emerged out recently, when researchers from *Technion and Ramban Hospital (Israel)* [3] succeeded in devising a methodology of testing a pooled sample of combined 64 individual specimens instead of testing all individual specimens explicitly. If the pooled sample resulted as positive, further testing of individual specimens done. On similar lines, Researchers from the *German Red Cross Blood Donor Service, Frankfurt* and the *Institute for Medical Virology at the University Hospital Frankfurt at Goethe University* [4] conducted the test on specimens of 50 patients by creating 10 mini-pools of 5 patient samples and simultaneously tested individual's specimens also.

This Pool Methodology is adopted in *Israel, Germany, South Korea* and India. In India, *Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR)* [5] has authorized some of the states (Utter Pradesh, West Bengal, Punjab,

Chhattisgarh and Maharashtra) for performing Pooled Sample Testing, with low positive density cases, in the proximity of less than 2%. For evaluation of pooled sample analysis, a pilot study [12] was conducted by health care professionals with the approval of All India Institute of Medical Sciences (AIIMS), Bhopal Institutional Human Ethics Committee

On the other side, in Computer Science, Binary Search Algorithm [2] is a data structure algorithm which is used for searching a particular item in the sorted array by comparing the middle item of an array collection. This algorithm is also known as Half Interval search and Binary Chop.

This article provides the theoretical analysis of how using the Principles of Binary Search Algorithm, there can be a further reduction in the number of testing kit requirements for identifying the individual specimen from a positive resulted pooled sample. In this modified methodology, instead of testing all individual samples of one pool, further mini sub- pools with lesser samples are tested recursively.

A. *What is the Pooled Sample Testing of Covid-19?*

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In the Pooled Sample Testing methodology, multiple specimens of different individuals are combined to form one single pool and this pooled sample is tested. If the result of the pooled sample turns out as negative then individual specimens are not tested because the result of all individual specimens pertaining to the negative resulted pooled sample will be automatically negative. In this negative pooled sample scenario, testing kits are saved by not testing the individual specimens. If the pooled sample resulted as positive, then there will be a minimum 1 positive specimen causing the positive result of a pooled sample. To trace out this individual positive specimen, testing of all individual specimens of the pooled sample needs to be done.

In India, as per the Indian Council of Medical Research ICMR [5], the pooling of samples was not recommended in areas or populations with positivity rates of >5% COVID-19. A preferable number of samples to be pooled is 5, though more than two samples can be pooled considering the higher possibility of missing positive samples with low viral load, it is strongly discouraged to pool more than 5 samples, except in research mode.

B. How Computer Science Binary Search Algorithm Works?

In the Data Structure domain of computer science, Binary Search Algorithm [2], searches the items in the sorted array collection by comparing the item with the middle index element and if element not found in the middle index then array elements are divided into two halves from the middle index. Now the item is searched again recursively in one half elements sub-array with the same middle index divide method. In another half sub-array no search is required.

II. MODIFIED POOLED TESTING METHODOLOGY USING PRINCIPLES OF BINARY SEARCH ALGORITHM

In existing Pooled Sample Testing, if the result of the Pooled sample is positive, then individual samples are tested explicitly. The numbers of test kit required for completing Pooled Testing depend on the number of individual positive specimens in pooled sample. In this new methodology, instead of performing the explicit testing of each individual specimen of the positive resulted sample, binary tree-structured [8] mini sub-pools formed with lesser number of specimens using the principles of Computer Science Data Structure [6]

Binary Search Algorithm and these mini sub-pools are tested recursively.

In India, the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) [5] recommended for using 5 samples per pool with an exception in research mode. *Rambam Medical Center and the Technion in Haifa, Isreal* [3] tested the Pooled Sample of 32 or 64 individual samples and *German Red Cross Blood Donor Service* formed mini-pool with 5 individual specimens. From the above examples of different countries, it seems there is no common consensus or standardization about pool size, i.e. what exact number of individual specimens should be mixed to form a pooled sample.

Let's do our study by taking 64 numbers of individual specimens per pooled sample; assuming that there is only 1 positive individual specimen out of 64 considering the fact that Pooled Sample Testing is recommended in low positivity rate scenario.

Step 1: In the Data Structure field of Computer Science, Binary Search Algorithm applicable for the sorted array of elements, so in first step, we will mark individual specimens with sequential ordering from 1 to 64.

Step 2: On getting positive results of a pooled sample constituted of 64 individual specimens, instead of testing all 64 samples, further 2 mini sub-pools are formed. The first mini sub-pool is formed using first 32 sequential marked individual specimens and second mini sub-pool is formed using the last 32 sequentially marked specimens as depicted in Figure 1.

Step 3: Two mini sub-pools of 32 samples formed in *Step 2* are tested again. As per our initial assumption, only 1 sample is positive out of 64, so out of two mini sub-pools of 32 individual specimens, one mini sub pool of 32 individual specimens will be positive and another mini sub-pool of 32 individual specimens will be negative. Now, assuming that individual positive specimen was in the first mini pool, so the test result of the first mini sub pool will be positive and the test result of the second mini sub-pool will be negative. Now, 32 individual specimens from the negative resulted mini sub pool will not require further individual specimen level testing. Only individual specimens of positive resulted mini subgroups require further testing.

Step 4: Now from the positive resulted mini sub-pool formed from 32 individual specimens in *Step 3*, further 2 mini sub-pools of 16 individual specimens are formed. And like *Step 3*, one mini sub-pool of 16 samples will

be positive and another mini sub-pool of 16 samples will be negative.

Step 5: This mini sub-pool formation process is iterated recursively with a lesser number of individual specimens. Initially, the sub-pool formation started with 32 individual specimens and later on, number of individual number of specimens are reduced in each step till pool size reduced to a single individual specimen per pool as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Formation of recursive mini sub-pools

C. Hybrid Methodology

Considering the complexities and manpower associated with the formation of multi-level mini sub-pool with varying numbers of individual specimens, a hybrid methodology can be adopted. In this approach at top levels of sub pool creation of Figure 1, earlier mentioned procedure from Step 1 to Step 3 or Step 4 can be followed, but at a lower level instead of further formation of mini sub pools, all individual specimens can be tested. E.g. in Figure 1 at level 5 from top, positive pool resulted in sample number from 17 to 20

can be tested individually instead of further sub-pool formation shown in Steps 6 and 7. By using this hybrid approach, the number of pool formations steps can be reduced.

III. MATHEMATICAL DERIVATION FOR CALCULATING NUMBER OF TESTING KITS REQUIREMENTS IN POSITIVE POOLED SAMPLE

This mathematical derivation calculates the number of testing kit required for identifying an individual specimen from the Pooled Sample. Let's understand Computer Science, Data Structure Binary Search Algorithm in terms of mathematics logarithmic function. If an array is sorted, then we can use the binary search technique [2] to search an n-element array in the order of $O(\log_2 n)$ comparisons, in a worst-case scenario. Since, $\log_2 n$ grows slowly as compare to the value of 'n' [7], here 'n' means number of elements. So, Binary Search is the optimal technique of searching an element in the sorted array scenario. Let's use the same principle in the case of COVID-19 Pooled Sample Testing.

Let 'k' be the number of comparisons required to search an element in an array of 'n' elements. As per the Binary Search Algorithm, the relation between 'k' and 'n' will be as $k = \log_2 n$. If the number of elements 'n' = 64, then $k = \log_2 64 \Rightarrow 6$

For creating a sorted array scenario, we will mark the individual specimen in sequential order. Let's mark it as 1 to 'n' for relating number of individual specimens in the pooled sample with the total number of elements in a sorted array.

As 'k' be the number of comparisons or sub-array in the context of binary search. But in the context of the pooled sample scenario, there are 2 comparisons on each level instead of 1 on each level of binary search as there is also requirement of testing of negative resulted mini sub-pool.

Let's calculate total number of testing kits that will be required for identifying individual specimens in pooled sample. Let's suppose total number of required kit(s) is 't', and the value of 't' in three different scenarios will be calculated as:

CASE 1: There is 1 positive specimen per pooled sample of 64 individual samples.

As explained earlier using the Binary Search Algorithm, $k = \log_2 n$, now there will be 2 comparisons on each level, 1 for positive resulted mini sub-pool sample and another one for the negative resulted sample. So, the

maximum number of testing kits requirement will be double of search comparisons in Binary Search.

Now the total maximum number of testing kits required to identify this 1 individual positive specimen will be calculated as

$$t=2k \Rightarrow 2\log_2 n \quad Eq.(1)$$

If 'n'=64 and 'k'=6 then for calculating 't' put the values of 'n' and 'k' in Eq.(1)

$$t= 2*6 =12$$

CASE 2: There are 2 positive specimens per pooled sample of 64 individual samples.

Now the total maximum amount of testing kits required to identify these 2 individual specimens will be calculated as

$$t= 2[k +(k-1)] \Rightarrow 2[(\log_2 n)+ ((\log_2 n)-1)] \quad Eq.(2)$$

Here we are adding (k-1) not (k) because to identify the second specimen, we have already tested a mini sub-pool on which first positive specimen was found. So for identifying the second specimen, the required number of testing kits will be 2 less as compared to the testing kits required to identify the first positive specimen.

If 'n'=64 and 'k'= $\log_2 64 \Rightarrow 6$, then to identify value of 't', put the values of 'n' and 'k' in Eq.(2)

$$t= 2*6+2*(6-1) \Rightarrow 12+10 \Rightarrow 22$$

CASE 3: There are 3 positive specimens per pooled sample of 64 individual samples. Now the total maximum amount of required testing kits to identify these 2 individual specimens will be calculated as

$$t= 2[k+(k-1)+(k-2)] \Rightarrow 2[(\log_2 n) +(\log_2 n -1)+((\log_2 n) -2)] \quad Eq. (3)$$

Like above Case 2 there will be addition of (k-2), it should also be noted that (k-1) or (k-2) should always positive number. If 'n'=64 and 'k'=6 then for calculating 't', put the values of 'n' and 'k' in Eq.(3)

$$t= 2*6+2*(6-1) +2*(6-2) \Rightarrow 12+10+8= 30$$

IV. DATA ANALYSIS ON DERIVED RESULT

As listed in Table 1, let's analyze the derivation result by varying the calculation parameters like by changing the number of individual specimens per sample from 64

to 2 and by changing the number of positive specimens from 1 to 3 per pool. From derived results, it came out that the number of required test kits depends upon the size of a pooled sample (number of specimens per pool). If the pool size is large then lesser kits will be required and in case of smaller pool size, more kits will be required for identifying individual specimens. The required number of testing kits will also depend upon the number of positive individual specimens per pooled sample.

Table 1: Derived Result by Varying Parameters

1 +ve specimen per Pooled Sample		
N	k= $\log_2 n$	t = $2*k$
64	6	$2*6 = 12$
32	5	$2*5 = 10$
16	4	$2*4 = 8$
8	3	$2*3 = 6$
4	2	$2*2 = 4$
2 +ve specimens per Pooled Sample		
N	k= $\log_2 n$	t = $2*k+2*(k-1)$
64	6	$2*6+2*(6-1) = 22$
32	5	$2*5+2*(5-1) = 18$
16	4	$2*4+2*(4-1) = 14$
8	3	$2*3+2*(3-1) = 10$
4	2	$2*2+2*(2-1) = 6$
3 +ve specimens per Pooled Sample		
N	k= $\log_2 n$	t= $2*k+2*(k-1)+2*(k-2)$
64	6	$2*6+2*(6-1)+2*(6-2)=30$
32	5	$2*5+2*(5-1)+2*(5-2)=24$
16	4	$2*4+2*(4-1)+2*(4-2)=18$
8	3	$2*3+2*(3-1)+2*(3-2)=12$
4	2	$2*2+2*(2-1)+2*(2-2)=6$

A comparative data analysis is also shown in Table 2 and Figure 2. In this analysis, a comparison is drawn between the testing kits required using existing methodology and saving of testing kits using new methodology based on the principles of Binary Search Algorithm.

In some of the cases where the pool size is small and the number of positive individual specimens per pool

are more than one e.g. when ‘n’=8 and ‘y’=3 then using this modified approach more testing kits will be required as compared to using existing methodology.

Table 2: Comparative Analysis of Required Testing Kits

No. of specimens per Pool (n)	No. of individual +ve per sample (y)	Required Kits/+ve Pool(using existing methodology)	Required Kits/+ve Pool (using Modified methodology)	Saving of Kits/Pool
64	1	64	12	52
32	1	32	10	22
16	1	16	8	8
8	1	8	6	2
4	1	4	4	0
64	2	64	22	42
32	2	32	18	14
16	2	16	14	2
8	2	8	10	-2
4	2	4	6	-2
64	3	64	30	34
32	3	32	24	8
16	3	16	18	-2
8	3	8	12	-4
4	3	4	6	-2

Figure 2: Requirements Kits Comparative Analysis

For calculating the required number of testing kits as shown in Table 2, a computer software program has been written in JAVA Programming Language. This

program takes 2 parameters as command line arguments, first input parameter as total number of samples in single a pool, and second input parameter as probable positive specimens per pool. On execution, the program calculates the required number of testing kits as an output parameter. The program is executed in windows CMD by varying command line arguments parameter value. Output result is shown in Figure 3.

Software Programme written in JAVA

```
import java.lang.*;
public class PoolTestKitCalculatorClass {
public static void main(String args[]) {
try {
System.out.println("-----");
System.out.println("First Parameter -
Total Numbers of Sample in Pool:
"+args[0]);
System.out.println("Second Parameter-
Postive Number of Specimens in Pool:
"+args[1]);
int cnt_pool_size =
Integer.parseInt(args[0]);
int cnt_postive_specimen =
Integer.parseInt(args[1]);
int required_testing_kits = 0;
boolean isvalidinput=false;
int calculate_log_value
=(int) (Math.log(cnt_pool_size) /
Math.log(2)) ;
for (int i = 0; i < cnt_postive_specimen;
i++)
{
if (calculate_log_value>
=cnt_postive_specimen){
required_testing_kits
=required_testing_kits+2*(calculate_log_v
alue-i);
isvalidinput=true;
}
}
if (isvalidinput){
System.out.println("Total Number of
Calculated Testing Kits: " +
required_testing_kits );
System.out.println("-----");
}
else {
System.out.println("Please enter Number
of Postive Specimen <= "+
calculate_log_value);
}
}
catch (Exception e) {
System.out.println("Error while executing
programme");
}
}}
```

```
Administrator: Command Prompt
C:\new_java>java PoolTestKitCalculatorClass 64 1
-----
First Parameter - Total Numbers of Sample in Pool: 64
Second Parameter- Postive Number of Specimens in Pool: 1
Total Number of Calculated Testing Kits: 12
-----
C:\new_java>java PoolTestKitCalculatorClass 64 2
-----
First Parameter - Total Numbers of Sample in Pool: 64
Second Parameter- Postive Number of Specimens in Pool: 2
Total Number of Calculated Testing Kits: 22
-----
C:\new_java>java PoolTestKitCalculatorClass 64 3
-----
First Parameter - Total Numbers of Sample in Pool: 64
Second Parameter- Postive Number of Specimens in Pool: 3
Total Number of Calculated Testing Kits: 30
-----
C:\new_java>java PoolTestKitCalculatorClass 32 1
-----
First Parameter - Total Numbers of Sample in Pool: 32
Second Parameter- Postive Number of Specimens in Pool: 1
Total Number of Calculated Testing Kits: 10
-----
C:\new_java>java PoolTestKitCalculatorClass 32 2
-----
First Parameter - Total Numbers of Sample in Pool: 32
Second Parameter- Postive Number of Specimens in Pool: 2
Total Number of Calculated Testing Kits: 18
-----
C:\new_java>java PoolTestKitCalculatorClass 32 3
-----
First Parameter - Total Numbers of Sample in Pool: 32
Second Parameter- Postive Number of Specimens in Pool: 3
Total Number of Calculated Testing Kits: 24
-----
```

Figure 3: Programme Execution Result in Terminal

V. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

It is quite evident from the various studies that pooled sample techniques may significantly save the resources compared to the individual sample testing. In a research paper published in Bulletin of the World Health Organization [11], it has been analyzed that using pooled sample testing strategy, 58-89 % fewer tests would be required for a pooled group size of 3 to 25 samples in a population of 150000 with an infection prevalence of 1 % or 5 %. In a pilot study[12] conducted by health care professionals of AIIMS(All India Institute of Medical Sciences), Bhopal, the diagnostic performance of qRT-PCR (quantitative reverse transcriptase PCR) on pooled sample was compared with that of individual samples and concluded that while pooling there is a reduction in the cost of diagnosis by 68% and the laboratory processing time by 66%.

From the comparative analysis illustrated earlier in this research paper, it can be concluded that using the the Principles of Computer Science Binary Search algorithm in Pooled Sample Testing, a significant amount of testing kits can be saved. It is also illustrated that the number of testing kits required to identify a positive specimen will depend upon the pool size, for a larger pool size, a lesser number of testing kits will be required and for smaller pools, a large number of testing kits will be required.

Further, the number of testing kits required is directly proportional to the number of positive specimens per pool. With the increase in positive specimens, the number of required testing kits will also increase

Pool testing can be used for mass testing and routine community survey [10] and, testing with correct methodology can significantly alleviate the strain on healthcare services in developing countries as during the initial days of COVID-19 outbreak, availability of testing kits was far less as compared to the population.

VI. FURTHER WORK

In the last decade, humankind has faced the disease outbreaks like H7N9 Avian Influenza, Ebola, Zika, Nipah and COVID -19 caused by the new sort of virus.

From the present crisis caused due to COVID-19 and past experiences of disease outbreaks caused due to viruses, in future the possibility of outbreak of disease causing by any new sort of virus cannot be ruled out.

For better preparedness and to withstand the fight against the microscopic enemy, capacity building with testing strategies could be the one of the key weapons of humankind. Automation of testing facilities can be one strategy that may provide the rapid test result of samples by testing hundreds or thousands of samples in one go. Such automation may require a concrete set of instructions based upon the predefined algorithm or mathematical formulae. The testing techniques illustrated in this paper or any other testing techniques with concrete steps could be the foundation stone of any new automation process.

This study may have a practical limitation as this is a theoretical hypothesis derived using the principles of Computer Science, Data Structure Binary Search algorithm, and there is also the risk of false-negative result in case of samples with low viral loads, but still, it may provide the avenue for future work.

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